

Organic Compounds of Potassium Metaperiodate, Arsenious Oxide, and Bismuth Trichloride

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Several organic compounds of KIO_4 , As_2O_3 , and $BiCl_3$ with organic bases have been prepared.

Although numerous organic compounds under the caption of complexes of potassium metaperiodate, arsenious oxide¹⁻², and bismuth trichloride³⁻¹² are found in literature, relatively little work has been done towards the formation of compounds with organic bases. The present communication deals with the preparation of compounds of potassium metaperiodate, arsenious oxide, and bismuth trichloride with some organic bases.

EXPERIMENTAL

Potassium metaperiodate and arsenious oxide of A.R. quality were employed. Bismuth trichloride was freed of any oxychloride, formed by the interaction of moisture, by dissolving in acetone of A.R. quality and removing any residue by filtration. Acetone solution, thus obtained, was used whenever required.

Butylⁿ amine (b.p. 77°) and quinoline (b.p. 238°) were purified by distillation, rejecting the first distillate (about 10% of the volume taken) in each case. Both dimethylamine and ethylenediamine, available in aqueous solution, were used as such. Benzidine was recrystallised from hot ethanol and the remaining bases were available in extra pure form.

Compounds of KIO_4 .—Solid potassium metaperiodate was dissolved slowly in a known volume of each of butylⁿ amine, dimethylamine, and piperidine in aqueous solution of suitable strength till saturation. The solution was warmed to bring any undissolved periodate into solution and then crystallised in a freezing mixture. The resulting crystalline compound was washed with acetone to remove any unchanged amine and dried *in vacuo*. On analysis it conformed to the molar ratio of the base to periodate as 1:1 (Table I, Expt. 1-3).

1. Reynold and Shive, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 650.
2. Banks *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1947, **69**, 927.
3. Belladen and Astengo, *Atti Accad. Lincei*, 1923, **i**, **32**, 491.
4. Dohn, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **48**, 275.
5. Challenger and Wilkinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **121**, 91.
6. Vanino and Musgnug, *Ber.*, 1917, **50**, 21.
7. Frost, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1954, **32**, 356.
8. Martini *Mikrochem.*, 1928, **6**, 28.
9. Byrkit and Dehn, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 1167.
10. Lapshina, Invest. Sektora Plating-i-drug., *Neorg. Khim. Akad. Nauk, S. S. S. R.*, 1955, **29**, 119.
11. Anand and Prasad, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1929, **301**, 311.
12. Lal *et al.*, *Ovrr. Sci.*, 1960, **29**, 272.

Compounds of As_2O_3 .—Similar addition of arsenious oxide, with successive heating and cooling, to butyl¹ amine yielded a gelatinous precipitate which on analysis after washing with ether and drying *in vacuo* gave the molar ratio of base to oxide as 2:1 (Table I, Expt. 4). With ethylenediamine, a yellow precipitate with molar ratio of base to oxide as 2:1 was obtained (Table I, Expt. 5). With piperidine, after cooling the saturated solution of arsenious oxide in a freezing mixture for about 48 hours, a dirty white crystalline mass with molar ratio of 1:1 was obtained (Table I, Expt. 6).

TABLE I

Expt. No.	Composition of the compound formed.	Analytical results(%).		Physical properties.
		Observed.	Calc.	
1	Butyl ¹ amine $C_4H_9NH_2 : KIO_4$	KIO_4 : 78.60 Amine : 21.40	79.20 20.80	White crystalline; readily soluble in water, insoluble in organic solvents, and not melting even up to 360°.
2	Dimethylamine $(CH_3)_2NH : KIO_4$	KIO_4 : 82.00 Amine : 18.00	83.60 16.40	White crystalline, turning yellow at 300° without melting; soluble in water but insoluble in organic solvents.
3	Piperidine $C_5H_{10}NH : KIO_4$	KIO_4 : 73.00 Base : 27.00	73.00 27.00	White solid; soluble in water, insoluble in organic solvents and not melting even at 300°.
4	Butyl ¹ amine 2 $C_4H_9NH_2 : As_2O_3$	As_2O_3 : 58.00 Amine : 42.00	57.60 42.40	Yellowish white crystalline; decomposing at 168°; sparingly soluble in water and insoluble in organic solvents.
5	Ethylenediamine 2 $NH_2CH_2CH_2NH_2 : As_2O_3$	As_2O_3 : 61.90 Amine : 38.10	62.30 37.70	Light yellow powder, m. p. 146-148°; soluble in water and insoluble in organic solvents.
6	Piperidine $C_5H_{10}NH : As_2O_3$	As_2O_3 : 71.00 Base : 29.00	70.00 30.00	Dirty white crystalline, not melting up to 300°; sparingly soluble in water and insoluble in organic solvents.
7	Quinoline $C_9H_7N : BiCl_3$	Bi : 46.30 Cl : 22.00 Base : 31.70	47.30 21.40 31.40	White powder, decomposing at 160°.
8	α -Picoline $CH_3C_7H_4N : BiCl_3$	Bi : 51.72 Cl : 25.23 Base : 23.05	51.20 26.10 22.70	White powder, fusing to a semisolid mass at 240°.
9	γ -Picoline $CH_3C_7H_4N : BiCl_3$	Bi : 51.20 Cl : 26.10 Base : 22.70	51.20 26.10 22.70	Pinkish white powder, decomposing at 310°.
10	Benzidine $NH_2C_6H_4C_6H_4NH_2 : BiCl_3$	Bi : 41.20 Cl : 22.40 Amine : 36.40	41.70 21.60 36.80	Yellow powder, turning green on exposure and decomposing at 300°.
11	Dimethylaniline $C_6H_5N(CH_3)_2 : BiCl_3$	Bi : 48.80 Cl : 24.30 Amine : 27.10	47.90 25.40 27.70	White solid, changing greenish and finally light yellow on exposure and decomposing at 139°.
12	Pyridine $C_5H_5N : BiCl_3$	Bi : 52.90 Cl : 26.30 Base : 20.80	53.00 27.00 20.00	White crystalline, softening at 230°.

Compounds of BiCl₃.—To acetone solutions of bismuth trichloride quinoline, α -picoline, γ -picoline, benzidine, dimethylaniline, and pyridine were slowly dropped separately in excess. The solid products on analysis (Bi³⁺ as oxychloride¹³ and Cl⁻ as silver chloride¹⁴) provided the molar ratio as 1:1 each. These are insoluble in organic solvents and decompose with water (Table I, Expts. 7-12).

DISCUSSION

In all these compounds N appears to be linked to iodine, arsenic, and bismuth through a co-ordinate link, resulting in the extension of the octet. Insolubility of these compounds in organic solvents and considerable solubility in water indicate a sufficient polarity in N—element bonds.

In the compounds with molar ratio of base to arsenious oxide as 2:1, a similar arrangement is suggested. Failure of the formation of 2:1 compound with piperidine may be due to steric effect. In order to balance the state of electronegativity in both the As atoms in the final product, a rearrangement of electrons from As=O to As $\rightarrow$ O, maintaining the octet of each As atom, is supposed to take place and the end product may be represented as:

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13. Scott, "Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis", 5th ed., Vol I, 1948, p. 143.
14. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 1960, p. 339.